
PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF VALEOLOGICAL CULTURE IN TEACHERS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7884894>

M.Yuldashev

*Teacher of theory and style of Physical Culture chair
Fergana State University*

The transition of our country to a market economy, the preservation of the health of the younger generation, as well as the whole nation, in promoting a culture of healthy living in high performance in the field of building a free, democratic society, renewing the morale of society, state and social construction has been studied as an important issue. The study of the essence of existing sources shows that in the early days of our society there was a social need for the decision-making of a healthy living culture, the creation of criteria that determine the level of existing living culture, shkn as well as practical actions were carried out on the way to satisfying this need. The future of any society depends on the growing young generation, on their health, spiritual wealth and perfection, on being folk and patriotic, on being educated and educated, and physically-mentally competent and mature.

Although in most times, such concepts as "active city", "mature state", "Kingdom of Justice", "perfect city "were used as equivalent concepts expressing the essence of "valeological culture", and the main focus was on the formation of spiritual and moral qualities in people, in a certain sense they served to illuminate aspirations on the path of healthy living and people After all, in the formation of a culture of healthy living, the spiritual and moral qualities of people were attached to them. In particular, strong-willed qualities such as character, strong will have arisen on the basis of having such qualities as hard work, truthfulness, putting the interests of others above their own. Acquaintance with the sources created in the framework of the problem in historical, philosophical, pedagogical and psychological directions confirms that the opinion expressed above is justified. In the era of the primitive community, when humanity lived unconsciously following the rule of natural laws and the principle of "struggle for survival," the emergence of the state and society at the next stage of development in itself caused the protection of State territories from enemies. On the basis of human health lies his

spiritual health. In the development of Industrial production, the importance of the spiritual boypig of a person is also great in its assessment, and spiritual wellness is also an important kuroli of social progress and economic progress. Therefore, the funds allocated to health care in progressive states are also high www.ziyouz.com the library will be at the level. So even the funds allocated for health sacking justify themselves to albat several times. In most states, the importance of hatgo as a socioeconomic criterion is also attributed to Kat in the first gal, with respect to the health importance of the World Health Organization. However, in some countries, spending on health care is mainly on clipic medicine and prophylactic medicine has fallen in the fall, although in fact it should be aimed at maintaining the health of healthy people and strengthening it. In such a takdir - a person is spiritually rich, physically rich, and only then will he bring wealth both to himself and to the state. Society-the state is socially-economically strengthened, and in which society - on the contrary-the degree of its downside of course also blurs a lot, unless the state has a sick sheet ("bulletin"). Therefore, such issues must first of all be given great importance by each person himself. Unfortunately, some people do not follow a simple - scientifically based "healthy lifestyle", do not care about its deep content. As a result, they are addicted to the trap of kamharakatlilna (hypodynamia) (1), quickly get old (2), head gays go fat at the expense of many ovulation (3), suffer from blood-vessel sclerosis (4), some suffer from diabetes mellitus (5), do not worry about what rest is (6), norms in life and production (7), constantly overbearing behavior bilai yash aydns (8), suffer from neurosis (9), are subjected to insomnia (10), and the airim who are more severe-distressed, end-woe and Baloi-ofag voluntarily, without knowing it, put Kadam. It is iarcomania (morphinism, toxicomania, drunkenness - alcoholism, smoking). This need meant that the defenders were physically strong. Therefore, special attention was paid to the physical maturation of young men in the ancient States of Greece and Rome. In particular, in ancient Greece, special attention was paid to the upbringing of adolescents, and methods were widely used that provided their physical conditioning. Therefore, the family and the main part of the educational process carried out at the state educational institution" agella " dab were organizing efforts to perform military Gymnastics exercises. Military Gymnastics would have focused on running, running over obstacles, jumping, throwing spears or discs, being able to fight using a hand or sword, and mastering the secrets of wrestling. As a result of a very strict upbringing, the young Spartans became physically contrived, fearless, brave warriors. Young Greeks also had to master the secrets of singing,

music, and dance. There was a view that these disciplines nurture the ability to feel beauty in adolescents and serve as an important basis in the formation of moral qualities.

By the Middle Ages, the idea of "risarlik rearing" was a priority in ensuring that young people matured physically and morally. According to the idea of this upbringing, they were obliged to master the following seven qualities: being able to ride a horse, fencing, spear fighting, swimming, hunting, playing checkers (or chess), singing and weaving poetry.

In the first four stages of human society, the views that human life is accompanied by nature in wakefulness, leading dates, natural habits that occur, have been interpreted as punishments sent by natural forces for negative behaviors committed by humans. The most optimal way to prevent such situations is to avoid harm to nature, preserve it and enrich it. In the essence of this idea, one of the main categories of healthy living culture finds its expression. In fact, nature also prevents the emergence of diseases in which the achievement of environmental purity is widespread among people and poses a serious threat to human health.

Of particular note is the thought of the zartushtiya Bible, the "Avesto", which advanced in this regard. In particular, in this work, a special place is allocated for personal and collective (social) hygiene issues. For example, as important source factors in the origin of various infectious diseases, such as hot and cold air, hunger, zinc oysters, is'temolization of spoiled food, cleanliness and non - compliance with environmental cleanliness, increased content of various poisonous insects (flies, flies, mites, mice, rats, etc.) and bad air (atmospheric pollution in modern interpretation) are cited. Another notable aspect of the work is that it outlines ways to achieve environmental cleanliness while addressing sanitary issues. In particular:

1. Hide debris, bury contaminated areas with soil, stones or ash. In this way, microbes are killed.

2. Fire, heat and cold lose in the medium. In "Avesto", fire is recognized as the most effective purifier and a means of eliminating danger. With fire, even clothes are neutralized.

3. Chemical way (ash, vinegar, wine, various herbs, bite, cadaf, onion, aloe, sandal, garlic, pepper, etc.) by smoking or dripping its water.

The ideas of Islam also provide valuable information on the promotion of views on the formation of spiritual and moral qualities among people, as well as the elimination of serious risk factors for human health. In particular, according to

the Quranic verses of Karim as well as the ideas presented in the Hadith, ensuring environmental cleanliness is an important factor in the health of those. In fact, environmental pollution creates an environment that promotes the reproduction of various microbes as well as their survival. Therefore, the hadiths expressed calls to keep housing clean, to follow personal hygiene, to clean the place where a person lives from what hurts him, as well as not to cut down trees that give shade to people, but, on the contrary, to do good deeds, such as planting trees.

The hadiths also note that habits that can be absorbed by a person, but negatively affect his health, in particular, the consumption of a drink (may), which ensures the sarhush of the organism, is a grave sin. After all, as a result of eating May, a person loses the opportunity to control his behavior, indulges in unethical activities. "...the drinker cannot be fulfilled at the same time, as he breaks from his faith while drinking." And Anas (ibn Malik) narrates: "the messenger of Allah Salalah alayhi Wa salam, and salam slapped a man who drank a drink with a palm branch and a plow. Abu Bakr Ersa, forty Darras were beaten", Saib in Yazid narrates: "in the auspicious times of Rasulullah sallallohu alayhu vasallam and in the years of Abu Bakr's reign and the early caliphate of Umar, we caught the mast and punishable by one beating of our hands, cowhams and clothes. By the last years of the Umar caliphate, forty Darras had been struck. Among the people, fisqu was delivered to the Saxon Darra when the facade was strengthened.", As stated in Hadith, places emphasis on the social importance of consuming a drink that sums up a person without being a personal business. In fact, the occurrence of such behavior by adults negatively affects, above all, the upbringing of young people, in which there is an interest in alcohol addiction and behavior as adults.

Activities aimed at promoting a culture of healthy living among the population, including young people, should ensure the formation of concepts in them about the essence of security measures to prevent the occurrence of extremely dangerous diseases.

It is advisable to strictly follow these thoughts in the process of an organized attitude towards a patient with various diseases.

In achieving a full understanding of the essence of the problem and the correct choice of its solution, it is important to study the current state of educational work in practice, aimed at the formation of a culture of healthy living in future teachers of Physical Culture.

REFERENCES:

1. Mamirzhon, Y. (2023, January). METHODOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF A VOLLEYBALL PLAYER. In e Conference Zone (pp. 28-40).
2. Ishmukhamedov, R., & Yuldashev, M. (2016). Innovative technologies in education and upbringing. T.: Germination.
3. Mamirjan, Y. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF VALELOGIC PHYSICAL CULTURE OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 8, 57-62.
4. Yuldashev, M., & Yakubova, G. (2022, October). RECOVERY IN ADAPTIVE PHYSICAL EDUCATION (REHABILITATION). In e Conference Zone (pp. 14-17).
5. Ishmukhamedov, R. J., & Yuldashev, M. (2013). Innovative pedagogical technologies in education and upbringing. T.: "Nihol" publishing house, 2016.
6. Maamirjan, Y., & Saminjan, X. (2022). SCHOOL-AGE IS THE NORM OF ACTION ACTIVITY (ACTIVITY). Conferencea, 75-78.
7. Yuldashev, M. (2021). Innovative Aspects For Healthy Lifestyle Formation And Development Of Sports. Current Research Journal Of Pedagogy, 2(05), 102-107.
8. PHYSICAL EXERCISE IN IMPROVING THE FITNESS OF 5TH-6TH GRADE LEARNERS. In e Conference Zone (pp. 18-29).
9. Khamroqulov, R. (2022, June). INCREASE GIRLS'PHYSICAL STATUS THROUGH ACTION GAMES. In e Conference Zone (pp. 234-237).
10. Rasuljan, K., & Mukhtasarkhon, R. (2022). ACTION GAMES ARE A FACTOR THAT INCREASES THE PHYSICAL FITNESS AND HEALTH OF GIRLS. American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 9, 11-20.
11. Rasuljan, K., & Mukhtasarkhon, R. (2022). ACTION GAMES ARE A FACTOR THAT INCREASES THE PHYSICAL FITNESS AND HEALTH OF GIRLS. American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 9, 11-20.
12. ABDUSATTAROVICH, K. R., & ALISHER, K. (2022, May). PLANNING OF THE EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING PROCESS OF YOUNG ATHLETES DURING EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES. In e Conference Zone (pp. 27-31).

13. Rasul, H., & Zulfiyakhon, M. (2022). FEATURES AND IMPORTANCE OF ACROBATIC EXERCISES. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 8, 31-39.
14. Dilshodovich, I. S. (2022). UMUM O'RTA TA'LIM MAKTABLARIDA O'G'IL BOLALARNI OILAGA TAYORLASHNING PSIXOLOGIK ILMIY ASOSLARI. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI, 2(14), 775-779.
15. Sherzod, I. (2022). THE CONTENT OF THE PREPARATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS FOR THE FORMATION OF FAMILISTIC COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 8, 40-46.
16. Ismoilov, S. D. (2022). OILA VA QADRIYAT. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(1), 998-1003.
17. Dilshodovich, I. S. (2021). Ways To Increase the Effectiveness of Physical Education Classes in Secondary Schools. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2, 142-143.
18. Ismoilov, S. (2021). Developing A Valued Attitude Towards the Family in Students as A Topical Pedagogical Problem. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 3, 91-93.
19. Khaitboevich, B. B. (2020). Some features of protection of students from the threat of harmful information in the educational process. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(10), 69-72.
20. Байджанов, Б. Х. (2020). Таълим жараёнида илғор хорижий тажрибаларни самарали қўллаш механизмлари. *Science and Education*, 1(2), 514-519.
21. Baydjanov, B. (2021, March). COMPATIBILITY OF NEW RENAISSANCE PEDAGOGY AND JADID ENLIGHTENERS' VIEWS ON EDUCATION AND INFORMATION SECURITY. In Конференции.
22. Baydjanov, B. (2021, June). HIGHER EDUCATION PROSPECTS AND ISSUES OF DEVELOPING INFORMATION SECURITY CULTURE AMONG STUDENTS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF FERGANA REGION). In Конференции.
23. Dilshodovich, I. S., & Muhammadjasur G'anijon o'g, I. (2022). O'SMIR YOSHDAGI O'G'IL BOLALARNI SHAXSINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA OILANING ROLI MAZMUNIGA ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR. *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 2(13), 466-471.

24. Dilshodovich, I. S., & Muhammadjasur G'anijon o'g, I. (2022). OILADA O'SMIR SHAXSNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING ASOSIY MANBALARI SHAXS RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR. INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022, 2(14), 57-65.

25. Dilshodovich, I. S., & Muhammadjasur G'anijon o'g, I. (2022). O'SMIR YOSHLARNI OILAVIY HAYOTGA TAYYORLASHDA OILA PEDAGOGIKASI VA PSIXOLOGIYA FANLARINING IMKONIYATLARI. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 3(25), 28-33.